

SYNTHESIS AND COMPRESSION BEHAVIOUR OF AL₂O₃-AL₃Ti IN SITU INTERMETALLIC MATRIX COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: Fully dense Al₂O₃-Al₃Ti intermetallic matrix composite containing 30vol.% Al₂O₃ particles was in situ processed by combining squeeze casting technique with combustion synthesis utilizing the reaction between TiO₂ powder and pure Al. Using XRD, DTA, SEM and TEM techniques, the reaction process and microstructure of the in-situ composite were examined. Compressive behaviour of the composite have been investigated at 25-600°C and compared with that of cast Al₃Ti alloy.

The in situ formed spherical α -Al₂O₃ particles with a size of 0.2-1 μ m are uniformly distributed in the Al₃Ti matrix. The grain size of the Al₃Ti matrix with a little amount of Al₂Ti precipitates is about 2-10 μ m. The in situ composite possess high compressive strength at room temperature up-to 600°C and is about six to nine times greater than that of cast Al₃Ti alloy. The high compressive strength of the composite is mainly attributed to the dispersion strengthening of Al₂O₃ particles through grain boundary strengthening and the increase of cleavage strength of Al₃Ti.

KEYWORDS: combustion synthesis, Al₂O₃-Al₃Ti, squeeze casting, compressive strength, strengthening mechanisms

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, much attention has been paid to the development and application of composites, such as metal matrix composite (MMC) and intermetallic matrix composite (IMC). Hundreds kinds of composites were manufactured and many fabrication processes were developed. Traditionally, composites have been produced by such processing techniques as powder metallurgy (PM), preform infiltration, spray deposition and various casting technologies, e. g. squeeze casting. In all the above techniques the reinforcement e.g. SiC whisker and particulate is combined with the matrix material. In this case the scale of the reinforcing phase is limited by the starting powder size, which is typically of the order of microns to tens of microns and rarely below 1 μ m.

In the last decade new in situ processing technologies for fabricating metal and ceramic composites have emerged. In situ techniques involve chemical reactions resulting in the formation of the reinforcement. Some of these technologies include SHS (Self-propagating High Temperature Synthesis), DIMOXTM, XDTM, VLS and MA (Mechanical Alloying) [1-6]. Due to the very fine and thermodynamically stable reinforcing phase, it is expected that the in

situ formed composites may reveal not only excellent dispersion of fine reinforcing particles, nascent interface, but also high thermodynamically stability and high temperature performance.

Al_3Ti has a lower density and probably better oxidation resistance than other Al-Ti intermetallic compounds. Such attractive characteristics also make Al_3Ti a potential candidate for low-density high-temperature structural material. But due to its low cleavage strength, the application is far limited. One way to improve the strength is to introduce reinforcements into Al_3Ti matrix. Unfortunately, few report was found.

Fukunaga [7] fabricated in situ composite by reaction squeeze casting between TiO_2 whisker and molten Al, but the microstructure of the composite is ununiform with the hardness ranging from Hv30 to Hv1050. Wang [8] et al prepared the TiO_2/Al bulks by squeeze cast and sintered them at 810°C and 910°C to produced $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Ti}_x\text{Al}_y$ in situ composite. These techniques related to high temperature synthesis, for instance, self-propagating high temperature synthesis (SHS), and the fatal weakness of this process is porous of the products. Therefore, many consolidation techniques were employed to make the product density. Such as SHS+HIP, SHS+Hot-extrusion[9]. Most of these techniques can provide high density, e.g., 99 pct of theoretical density, but also incur an economic penalty.

The relatively high porosity in the products are thought to be due mainly to (1) the low density of the reactant mixture resulting in outgasing during reaction (2) intrinsic volume changes between reactants and products in the combustion synthesis reaction. If the density of the reactant is increased, the density of the products is expected to be improved. But for the powder-SHS process, it is impossible to achieve full-density reactant, and high green density will result in high ignition temperature.

In this paper, the fully dense $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Al}_3\text{Ti}$ in situ composite was synthesized by reaction between TiO_2 powder and molten Al via squeeze casting route. The method combines the synthesis and the densification steps into a one-step process.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The anatase TiO_2 powder with the average diameter of $0.6\mu\text{m}$ and pure Al (99.7%) were employed as the raw materials. TiO_2/Al bulks with 35% volume fraction of TiO_2 (determined according to the reaction formula) were prepared by squeeze casting method[7]. Subsequently, the squeeze-cast TiO_2/Al bulks were heat treated to form final $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Al}_3\text{Ti}$ composite in a special medium.

Using DTA, XRD, SEM and TEM techniques, the reaction process and the microstructure of the composites were investigated in details. The TEM foils were prepared by conventional procedure which involved cutting discs with diameter of 3.0 mm, mechanical polishing them to $50\mu\text{m}$, and dimpling to $20\mu\text{m}$ and finally ion milling. SEM and TEM observations were carried out on S-570 and EM420, respectively. Compression test at strain rate $4.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{s}^{-1}$ were conducted in Gleeble1500 test machine to failure in most cases. The specimens ($\phi 9 \times 20 \text{ mm}$) were prepared by electro-discharge machining and grinding. The composites density were determined by water immersion technique.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthesis Process

Thermodynamic Background

The free energy of formation (ΔG_T) of TiO_2 , and Al_2O_3 were calculated according to the function of free enthalpy of substance[10]. The results indicated that the reaction between TiO_2 and Al to form Al_2O_3 was possible. The reaction heat (ΔH_T) under different temperature were also calculated and the results show that the reaction between TiO_2 and Al is an exothermic reaction. The reaction formula used for thermodynamic calculation are as follows:

and

in general:

In case of $T=1200K$, the theoretical adiabatic temperature of Eqn 1 (T_{ad}) is about 2300K. This temperature is slightly lower than the melt point of Al_2O_3 , but higher than that of Al and Ti.

Squeeze Casting Process and DTA Analysis

During the squeeze casting process for TiO_2/Al , the TiO_2 powder was directly pressed to fabricate preform with a determined volume fraction ($V_f=35\%$). The infiltration and compound were achieved between TiO_2 and Al. The processing parameters were shown in Table 1. No reaction occurred through the squeeze casting process. According to the reaction dynamics, the reaction can be achieved by farther increasing the temperature, but this is limited in squeeze casting technique. Subsequently, the heat characteristic of the reaction between TiO_2 and Al was shown by the differential thermal analysis (DTA) curve in Fig.1. The results indicated that an exothermic reaction occurred in the range $750^\circ C-820^\circ C$ after Al in the cast block had molten in the range $660^\circ C-670^\circ C$.

Table 1: The processing parameters for TiO_2/Al bulk materials

Tm ($^\circ C$)*	Td ($^\circ C$)	Tp ($^\circ C$)	P (MPa)	τ (s)
800-820	500-550	500-550	30-31	20-25

* Tm, Td, Tp- the temperature of molten Al, die and preform, respectively.
P- applied pressure, τ - dwell time of pressure

Reaction Process Achieved by Heat Treatment

According to the results of DTA, the reaction between TiO_2 and Al was achieved by heat treatment. The squeeze cast TiO_2/Al blocks were heated in a special medium in furnace and the process were examined through the observation window. When the temperature reached to $800^\circ C$ indicated by the thermometer, the exothermic reaction usually began simultaneously.

Fig.1: DTA curve showing an exothermic reaction of TiO_2/Al block

High exothermicity result in high brightness of the blocks. Occasionally, the reaction began locally at one point or side and propagated to the whole blocks in a short time. This is the same as the propagation of the combustion wave in SHS. A typical combustion wave propagating process recorded by an auto camera with a rate of 2.5 pictures per second was shown in Fig. 2.

Fig.2: The true SHS process of TiO_2/Al to produce in situ composite

In order to characterize the changes of the microstructure, the microhardness of SHS sample with unreacted part were determined from unreacted area to reacted area by a microsclerometer with a load of 5Kg and a dwell time of 10s, the result was shown in Fig.3. The size of the transition region was about 1 mm, the hardness changed significantly with a microhardness increment of more than 600. This indicated that the material was strengthened remarkably after the reaction.

Fig.3: Microhardness changes from unreacted area to reacted area of the SHS sample

Microstructure and its Formation Mechanisms

No reaction occurs during the squeeze casting process for TiO_2/Al bulk materials (Fig.4a). There are only $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and Al_3Ti peaks in the X-ray diffractograph (XRD) of the products produced from TiO_2/Al (Fig.4b), i.e., the product were composed of Al_2O_3 and Al_3Ti . This indicated that the reaction between TiO_2 and Al had taken place to form Al_3Ti and Al_2O_3 . According to Eqn 3, the formation of 1 volume of Al_2O_3 will be followed by 2.26 volume of Al_3Ti . So the product is Al_2O_3 reinforced Al_3Ti matrix composite.

Fig.4: X-ray diffraction pattern of as-cast TiO_2/Al bulk(a) and reaction product(b)

A typical scanning electron micrograph of the composites were shown in Fig.5 which indicated that the densities of the composites are more than 98 pct of the theoretical density (the density of the composites is 3.56g/cm^3 and the theoretical density of Al, Al_2O_3 and Al_3Ti used in calculation is 2.7g/cm^3 , 3.99g/cm^3 and 3.37g/cm^3 , respectively). The reinforcement produced by reaction are very fine, uniform distribution and in particulate-shape in the matrix. The dimension of the particles is less than $1\mu\text{m}$. The dark zone was Al_3Ti matrix. If the volume fraction of TiO_2 in the TiO_2/Al blocks is further lowered, we can get the Al_2O_3 and Al_3Ti mixing reinforced aluminium matrix composite (MMC).

Fig.5: Typical SEM micrograph of in situ composite

TEM observations gave more information of the microstructure as shown in Fig.6. Block-like and particle-shape Al_3Ti phase with a relative large dimension ($2\text{-}10\mu\text{m}$) formed in the composite (Fig.6a), but this size is much smaller than the grain size of cast Al_3Ti alloy (about 1 mm) [11]. Fine grain may be beneficial to the strength of materials. Many Al_2O_3 particles were dispersed around or within Al_3Ti phases (Fig.6b,c). Helix dislocations were also observed in Al_3Ti phases as shown in Fig.6c. Besides these, a strip-like precipitates were found in the Al_3Ti matrix (Fig.6d). These phase were determined to be Al_2Ti precipitates.

Fig.6: TEM images of the microstructure of the composite

Based on the results presented above and thermodynamic calculation, the following is believed to be the mechanisms for the reaction synthesis:

First, the reaction between TiO_2 and Al to produce Al_2O_3 particles and [Ti]. Subsequently, a solidification process between remained Al and Ti displaced from the reaction to form nascent Al_3Ti matrix and Al_2Ti precipitates. According to the aluminium-titanium equilibrium diagram, these results can be well understood[12]. During this process, the distribution of Al_2O_3 particles produced by the first reaction process would be influenced.

Compressive Behaviour and Strengthening Mechanisms

Load versus displacement curves of the in situ composite compressed under different temperature is shown in Fig.7. The curve of TiO_2/Al bulk materials is also presented for comparison. The obtained values of yield stress are plotted as a function of temperature in Fig.8. In the tested temperature range, the curves have a common feature: after yielding, load begin to decrease and soon the curves are terminated by fracture, fracture often precedes yielding except that of TiO_2/Al as seen in Fig.7. Such a small fracture strain relatively mean that the composite does not exhibit any ductility in this temperature range. This is because of the native brittleness of Al_3Ti with DO_{22} -type structure and presence of large amount of Al_2O_3 particles.

Fig.7: Load versus displacement curves of the composite compressed under different temperatures

The yield stress increase gradually from 1200 MPa to 1566 MPa with increasing temperature up to about 300°C and then decrease rapidly until about 600°C. But the compressive strength also maintained at 645 MPa at 600°C. The strength of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Al}_3\text{Ti}$ composite is about six to nine times greater than that of unreinforced cast Al_3Ti alloy in the tested temperature range as shown in Fig.8.

Based on these results and microstructural examination, the following is believed to be the strengthening mechanisms for the composite:

The dominant mechanism is dispersion strengthening performed through grain boundary strengthening and increase of cleavage strength of Al_3Ti matrix, i.e., the presence of fine Al_2O_3 particles impeded propagation of the cleavage cracks in the matrix. Besides, the dislocations and fine grain strengthening are also beneficial to the strength of the composite.

Fig.8: Compressive strength of the composite as a function of temperature. The compressive yield strength of cast Al_3Ti alloy is also shown for comparison

CONCLUSIONS

The differential thermal analysis (DTA) of squeeze-cast TiO_2/Al bulk indicated that an exothermic reaction occurred after the temperature reached to 750°C . The reaction between TiO_2 and Al is a high exothermicity reaction. A high temperature combustion synthesis of fully dense $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{Al}_3\text{Ti}$ in situ composite were successfully achieved for squeeze-cast TiO_2/Al blocks by heating the blocks in a special medium.

Very fine-scale and excellent dispersion of reinforcing phase (Al_2O_3 particles) ranging from 0.2 to $1.0\mu\text{m}$ were obtained in the Al_3Ti matrix. The discussion on the reaction mechanisms concluded that the in situ process include a reaction process and a solidification process.

The in situ composite possess high compressive strength at room temperature up to 600°C and is about six to nine times greater than that of cast Al_3Ti alloy. The dominant strengthening mechanism is dispersion strengthening performed through grain boundary strengthening and increase of cleavage strength of Al_3Ti matrix.

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